

STRUCTURE OF REFLECTIVE ACTIVITY OF FUTURE TEACHERS AND DIRECTIONS FOR ITS DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract. This article discusses the need for the formation of reflection skills in future teachers, its specific features, the relationship between reflexive activity and cultural outlook, the role of pedagogical reflection in the teacher's professional activity, the components of pedagogical reflection, their content, their functions, and the possibility of eliminating stereotypes in the teacher's thinking. The article serves as a resource for the scientific-pedagogical community, students, and researchers.

The issue of the formation of pedagogical reflection in future teachers has been studied by many experts, including I.A. Stetsenko, who has paid special attention to this issue, expressed his views on the teacher's pedagogical reflection, and thought about its complex structural structure.

The specialist has shown that the psychological structure of pedagogical reflection consists of motivational-purposeful, cognitive-operational, affective, evaluative, and moral-volitional parts. The content of the motivational-objective element of the teacher's reflection activity consists of the future teacher's need for reflexive activity, his positive attitude towards reflection, his interests in the field of improving his activities related to pedagogical reflection, and his understanding of the purpose of reflexive activity. The content of the cognitive-operational element of reflexive activity includes knowledge clarifying the theoretical basis of pedagogical reflection and professional skills related to the implementation of reflexive activity.

The affective component of pedagogical reflection includes the teacher's feelings, experiences, and confidence in success directed at the implementation of actions in the process of pedagogical reflection.

The content of the evaluative element of pedagogical reflection can include the self-evaluation of the future teacher and actions related to controlling reflexive activity.

The content of the moral-volitional element of pedagogical reflection includes personal qualities that allow effective reflexive activity.

Specialists also tried to research the role of teachers' reflexive activity in the pedagogical process. The results of the study of self-development and improvement of one's own activity and a teacher's reflexive activity by scientists show that, as a result of reflexive evaluation, teachers develop a positive attitude towards themselves and the teaching profession. The development of reflexive processes and the ability to reflect will help to eliminate arrogance in mental activity. This is evident in stereotypes based on one-sided approaches to problems. Pedagogical reflection is important in ensuring that future teachers can approach themselves and their profession from the perspective of others. With the help of pedagogical reflection, a professional and cultural worldview is formed in future teachers. By accepting different perspectives, future teachers are able to focus their creative thinking. As a result, he gets rid of his one-sided views and broadens his cultural outlook. This problem is based theoretically, pedagogically, and psychologically on R. Safarova, B. Mamurov, G. Ibrahimova, S. L. Rubinshtein, and I. N. Semenov.

Future teachers cannot become the subjects of their personal and professional activities without having the skills of reflexive activity. Personal-professional creativity, professional-cultural worldview, and professional competence will develop in a reciprocal manner in future teachers only as a result of acquiring the skill of reflexive activity. Future teachers will be able to perform the following functions with the help of reflexive skills in the course of their future professional activities: They are:

1. To ensure professional self-determination and professional adaptation in the process of acquiring pedagogical activity.
2. To have the experience of a conscious attitude towards practical pedagogical activities.
3. To demonstrate the skills of managing one's own pedagogical activities in a systematic, integrated manner.
4. To ensure productive, innovative activity in creative thinking.
5. Implementation of creative actions related to the regular development of productive pedagogical activity.
6. Level of professionalism, pedagogical skills, professional competence, regular personal and professional development, ensuring personal development based on self-assessment, self-analysis, and management of one's own activities, demonstrating the ability to expand professional and cultural outlook.

7. Protecting future teachers from professional deformation, pedagogical crises, and pedagogical exhaustion.

Recognition of pedagogical reflection for the teacher in the process of pedagogical activity increases the need to use technologies of reflexive activity. The use of these technologies in the pedagogical process allows for the systematic development of reflexive competence in future teachers. The process of developing the reflexive activity of the future teacher is a pedagogical process of an integrative nature, which includes the components of the teacher's personality and allows for the determination of the strategy for developing his pedagogical activity. It is known that reflexive activity is a unique expression of the teacher's pedagogical thinking. Among most pedagogical situations, situations that engage teachers in reflection are of particular importance for their professional development. As a result of reflection, teachers clearly see their mistakes and determine their future actions.

Teachers need pedagogical reflection in order to make the necessary decisions in the process of directly interacting with students. As a result of the insufficient formation of pedagogical reflection, teachers cannot clearly see their mistakes and face difficulties in carrying out productive activities. In most cases, in decision-making in interactive situations, teachers approach the problem impulsively rather than reflexively. In this process, they rely on intuition rather than reason. This prevents them from making effective decisions. In such situations, the ineffective actions of the teacher are manifested as follows:

- having difficulty accepting the viewpoints of their students and colleagues;
- the inability of the teacher to fully understand the problems when making decisions, which indicates that the ability to reflect is not sufficiently formed in them. the presence of arrogance in the teacher's thinking;
- in this process, the teacher designs and implements the educational process without reflecting on the students' activities. However, it does not consider why students' attainment levels are low. stereotypes in the teacher's thinking;
- they are manifested in making decisions in conflict situations, not paying attention to reflections of students' behaviour in situations where they do not want to study.
- In these situations, the teacher is subject to existing stereotypes in his thinking. In such situations, the teacher blames the students for not wanting to study, not being able to study, and having negative behavior. does not focus on the closedness of their intellect. Because the teacher lacks reflective skills, he does not focus on finding out what students want and how to work with them. On the

one hand, this is explained by the fact that the teacher's reflection skills are not sufficiently developed, and on the other hand, he does not have a cultural outlook. the presence of coercion in the teacher's thinking;

In such situations, they do not follow the rules of the culture of interpersonal relations, knowing themselves to be right. It can be seen that the formation of reflexive skills in future teachers is one of the important tasks of the higher pedagogical education process and is a specific condition for the development of the teacher's pedagogical culture.

References:

1. Стеценко И.А. Педагогическая технология подготовки учителя к рефлексивной деятельности // Известия ТРТУ. 2006. №2. С. 171-176
2. R.G.Safarova. Kognitiv pedagogikaga oid nazariy yondashuvlar. Monografiya. – Toshkent: “Science and innovation”, 2024. – 186 b.
3. Маъмуров Б.Б. Бўлажак ўқитувчиларда акмеологик ёндашув асосида таълим жараёнини лойиҳалаш кўникмаларини ривожлантириш тизими. Пед. фан. док (DSc) илмий даражасини олиш учун ёзилган дис.... – Тошкент, 2018. – 263 б.
4. Рубинштейн, С.Л. Основы общей психологии / С.Л. Рубинштейн. - СПб.: Питер, 2002. - 720 с.
5. Ибрагимова Г. Интерфаол ўқитиш жараёнида бўлажак ўқитувчиларда креатив функцияни ривожлантириш. – Т.: “BAYOZ”, 2011. – 52 б

